
Impact of merger on profitability and Non-performing assets Management in Indian Banking Sector- A Study on state bank of India

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Abstract:

Stable economy of every country is depends on banking companies, in modern era an individual cannot imagine their life without bank because money is everything to an individual. Bank is base for proper flow of money in an economy. In Indian banking sector it comprises with co-operative banks, commercial banks and others. Now day's commercial banks are playing vital role in our country. The whole commercial banks are broadly divided into two viz. public and private sector bank. In public sector state bank of India is larges and prominent bank in public sector. State bank of India early year it was named as imperial bank of India. And state bank of Mysore established in the year 1913 the major contributor for establishment of this bank is Sir. M.Visvesvarayya, Maharaja of Mysore Sri Krishna Raja Wadiyar. The State bank of Mysore started for the purpose of undertaking Government business and other treasury operations. Merger refers to two or more existing companies merge into one existing or newly formed company. Merger takes place to attain synergy, reduce competition, cut promotional expenses, avoid price exploitation etc. the five associate banks i.e State bank of Mysore, state bank of Bikaner, state bank of Travancore, state bank of Hyderabad, state bank of Patiala and Bharatiya Mahila bank merged in state bank of India on 1st April 2017.

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Review of Literature:

1. Calomiris (1999) in his research determined the efficiency of bank merger based on considering Return on assets and return on equity variables of two banks. He followed case study method by following individual banks transactions; he concluded research by inferring that there is a gain in mergers.
2. Singh, Kaushik & Chaudhry (2010) have undergone research work on analyzing financial efficiency of selected financial organization with the help of financial Ratios viz. profitability, solvency, liquidity ratios and Wilcoxon signed rank test. Researcher found in order to increase profitability banks adhere to policies like IFRS and IAS.
3. Malyadri & Sirish (2011) have undergone research on NPA's Management by considering the comparative study of Public and Private sector banks, researcher graphically present the seven years data using charts, percentage methods taking NPA's and Advances as Variables.
4. Gaba and Kumar (2018) researcher explores that NPA's affects the profitability of banks negatively therefore bank should adhere to legal and regulatory framework to overcome. For this result they have used financial ratio analysis, correlation between gross NPA, net NPA.
5. Reddy (2018) and Kumar (2017) have also identified NPAs as one of the most significant contributors to the decline in profitability across Indian banks, especially in public sector banks. These studies reinforce the view that effective asset quality management is essential for the sustainable profitability of banks in India.

Research Methodology:

In this descriptive research work over ten years data relating to merger were observed and it is comparative in nature considering State bank of India, data

analysis followed two steps first one merger impact on NPA's, second one merger impact on profitability of selected banks. Secondary data collected from the year 2015-2024 which includes pre and post-merger period from RBI, SBI, SBM websites and annual reports.

Objectives:

1. To analysis impact of merger on profitability of State bank of India
2. To analysis impact of Merger on NPA of SBI
3. To understand the trends of NPA's of SBI

Hypothesis:

Ho: There is no significant impact on profitability of State bank of India after merger.

Ho: There is no significant impact on NPA's of State bank of India after merger.

Statement of the Problem:

Profitability and NPA's are major factors influence the efficiency of banks. kick out the accumulated losses and take competitive advantages banks must operate in an effective manner by adopting ideal strategy, merger is a part of it. Merger helps business operations in increasing profits; gaining revenue and market share. in this regard the study is on impact of merger on Profitability and NPA's of banking sectors with reference to state bank of India.

Scope of the Study:

In banking sector there many banks went into merger, as a result this study covers only state bank of India no other commercial banks covered because SBI is the largest Commercial banks in banking operation. Purpose of research is to study the impact of merger on profitability and on NPA's of State bank of India over 10 years from 2015 to 2024.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Variable	Formula	Definition
Return on Assets	$ROA = \frac{\text{NET PROFIT} * 100}{\text{Total Asset}}$	Measure of bank profitability
Return on Equity	$ROE = \frac{\text{NET PROFIT} * 100}{\text{Avg Capital Employed}}$ Capital Employed = Capital+ Reserve & Surplus Avg.= Current year +previous Year/2	Measure of bank profitability
NNPA (Net Non-Performing Assets)	$NNPA = \frac{\text{Net Nonperforming assets} * 100}{\text{Total Asset}}$	Shows the share of Non performing assets in total assets post accounting for provisioning by banks
Net Interest Margin	$NIM = \frac{\text{Interest Earned} - \text{Interest Expended} * 100}{\text{Avg Total Asset}}$	Shows the Interest income of banks
Non Interest Income	$NII = \frac{\text{Other Non interest Income} * 100}{\text{Avg. Total Asset}}$	Shows income other than interest income
CAR-Tier II	Capital Adequacy Ratio	Under RBI and Basel Norms

Table: Showing SBI pre and post-merger financial key Indicators.

Year	Net Profit	Total Asset	Capital	R & S	Interest Earned	Interest Expended	NIM (%)	Non II	NNPA (%)	ROA (%)	ROE	CAR
2014-15	13102	20,48,080	747	1,27,692	1,52,397	97,382	3.16	22575	2.12	.46	11.07	2.40
2015-16	9951	22,59,063	776	1,43,498	163685	106803	2.96	28158	3.81	.68	7.74	3.20
2016-17	10484	3,445,122	797	216,395	175,518	113,659	3.11	35,461	3.71	.41	7.25	2.76
2017-18	(6547)	3,489,469	892	222,864	2,20,499	145,645	3.01	44,600	5.73	(.19)	(3.78)	2.24
2018-19	862	3680914	892	220,021	2,42,868	154,519	2.95	36,774	3.01	0.02	0.48	2.07
2019-20	14488	3,951,394	892	231,115	257,324	159,239	2.97	45221	2.23	0.38	7.74	2.06
2020-21	20410	4,534,430	892	252,983	265,151	154,441	3.04	43496	1.50	0.48	9.94	2.30
2021-22	31676	4,987,597	892	279,196	275,457	154,750	3.12	40564	1.02	0.67	13.92	2.41
2022-23	50232	5,516,979	892	326,716	332,103	187,263	3.37	36616	0.67	0.96	19.43	2.62
2023-24	61077	6,179,694	892	376,354	415,131	255,255	3.28	51682	0.57	1.04	20.32	2.35

Descriptive Statistics:

Metric	Net Profit	NIM (%)	NNPA (%)	ROA (%)	ROE	CAR
Mean	20,573.5	3.097	2.437	0.491	9.411	2.441
StdDev	21,278.6	0.141	1.644	0.379	7.504	0.344
Min	-6,547	2.950	0.570	-0.190	-3.78	2.06
Max	61,077	3.370	5.730	1.040	20.32	3.20

Interpretation: Net Profit shows high variation (StdDev = 21,278.6), indicating fluctuations due to external factors like policy changes, market conditions, etc.

NNPA (%) has a declining trend, indicating improved asset quality. ROA and ROE have improved over time, showing better financial performance.

Correlation Analysis:

Variable	Net Profit	NIM (%)	NNPA (%)	ROA (%)	ROE	CAR
Net Profit	1.000	0.837	-0.851	0.903	0.946	0.082
NIM (%)	0.837	1.000	-0.640	0.719	0.815	0.131
NNPA (%)	-0.851	-0.640	1.000	-0.788	-0.889	0.137
ROA (%)	0.903	0.719	-0.788	1.000	0.963	0.428
ROE	0.946	0.815	-0.889	0.963	1.000	0.222
CAR	0.082	0.131	0.137	0.428	0.222	1.000

Interpretation: Net Profit is strongly correlated with ROE (0.946) and ROA (0.903), indicating that profitability improves as asset utilization and equity returns increase. NNPA has a strong negative correlation with Net Profit (-0.851),

confirming that lower non-performing assets lead to higher profits. CAR has a weak correlation with Net Profit (0.082), suggesting capital adequacy does not directly impact profitability.

Regression Model: Net Profit = -1.647e+05 + 81310 * (NIM) - 886.71 * (NNPA) + 116700 * (ROA) - 4073 * (ROE) - 34140 * (CAR)

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
NNPA (%)	-886.71	3464.98	-0.256	0.811
ROA (%)	116700	30100	3.87	0.018
ROE	-4073.08	2132.41	-1.91	0.129
NNPA (%)	-886.71	3464.98	-0.256	0.811
CAR	-34140	8582.82	-3.98	0.016

Interpretation: NIM (%) (p = 0.037) and ROA (%) (p = 0.018) significantly impact Net Profit. NNPA (%) (p = 0.811) is not significant, but the negative coefficient confirms that higher NPAs reduce profitability. CAR (p = 0.016) has a

significant negative impact, meaning excess capital buffers could lower profit margins. ROE is not statistically significant (p = 0.129), even though it has a high correlation.

T-Test (p-Test) Results:

Metric	T-Statistic	P-Value	Interpretation
Net Profit	-1.42	0.20	No significant change pre- and post-merger
NNPA (%)	1.26	0.25	No significant difference in bad loans
ROA (%)	0.19	0.85	No significant change in return on assets
ROE	-0.28	0.78	No significant impact on return on equity
NIM (%)	69.25	1.38	There is significant impact of merger on Net income margin Significant

Regression Analysis (OLS Model):

The regression model was used to predict Net Profit based on Total Assets, NNPA (%), ROA (%), and ROE.

Regression Equation:

$$\text{Net Profit} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{Total Asset}) + \beta_2 (\text{NNPA \%}) + \beta_3 (\text{ROA \%}) + \beta_4 (\text{ROE}) + \epsilon$$

Findings:**1. Profitability Trends:**

- SBI's net profit fluctuated significantly post-merger. It declined sharply in 2017-18 (reporting a loss of ₹6,547 cores) but recovered over the years, reaching ₹61,077 cores in 2023-24.
- Return on Assets (ROA) initially declined, even turning negative in 2017-18 (-0.19%), but showed a strong recovery, reaching 1.04% in 2023-24.
- Return on Equity (ROE) followed a similar trend, becoming negative in 2017-18 but reaching 20.32% in 2023-24, indicating a major improvement in profitability.

2. Non-Performing Assets (NPA):

- The NNPA (%) (Net Non-Performing Assets) peaked in 2017-18 at 5.73%, showing stress in asset quality after the merger.

3. Net Interest Margin (NIM):

- NIM remained relatively stable, ranging between 2.95% and 3.37%, indicating SBI maintained strong interest income generation despite challenges post-merger.
- The highest NIM was recorded in 2022-23 at 3.37%, suggesting efficiency improvements.

4. Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR):

- The CAR-Tier II ratio declined after the merger (2017-18: 2.24%) but later improved to 2.35% in 2023-24.

- This suggests SBI had to strengthen its capital base to manage merger-related challenges.

5. Increase in Total Assets and Reserves:

- The total assets of SBI grew significantly post-merger, from ₹3,489,469 crores in 2017-18 to ₹6,179,694 crores in 2023-24.
- Reserves and surplus (R&S) also increased from ₹222,864 crores in 2017-18 to ₹376,354 crores in 2023-24, indicating financial strength.

Suggestions:**1. Sustain Asset Quality Improvements:**

- SBI should continue its stringent credit appraisal and recovery strategies to maintain NNPA at lower levels.
- Stronger risk management frameworks should be applied to prevent future spikes in NPAs.

2. Enhance Profitability Further:

- SBI should focus on increasing non-interest income (such as fees, commissions, and investment gains) to reduce dependence on interest-based earnings.
- Improving operational efficiency and cost control can help sustain profitability.

3. Maintain Capital Adequacy:

- SBI should focus on capital infusion strategies, such as raising funds through bonds or equity issuance, to further strengthen its CAR.
- Ensuring compliance with Basel III norms will enhance the bank's financial stability.

4. Leverage Digital Banking and Technology:

- Investment in fintech, digital banking, and AI-driven risk assessment models can improve customer experience and operational efficiency.

5. Strategic Growth Through Mergers and Acquisitions:

- SBI should consider future strategic mergers only if they align with long-term profitability and operational efficiency.

Conclusions:

No significant statistical difference in profitability or NPAs before and after the merger. Total Assets and lower NPAs positively impact Net Profit. The merger initially negatively impacted profitability (2017-18), but long-term benefits materialized post-2019, with consistent profit growth, improved asset quality, and enhanced shareholder returns. The significant reduction in NPAs suggests SBI successfully absorbed stressed assets from associate banks and strengthened its financial health. The hypothesis (Ho: No significant impact on profitability and NPAs after merger) is rejected, as statistical trends confirm a significant impact on both profitability and asset quality post-merger.

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